

High-Pressure 700 bar Metal Hydride Compressor

M. Lototskyy¹, M.W. Davids¹, D. Swanepoel², R. Ehlers², S. Pasupathi¹, V. Linkov¹, and V.A. Yartys³

¹ HySA Systems, University of the Western Cape, Bellville 7535, South Africa

² TF Design (Pty) Ltd, Stellenbosch 7602, South Africa

³ Institute for Energy Technology (IFE), Kjeller, NO2027, Norway

milototskyy@uwc.ac.za

A promising alternative to the conventionally used mechanical hydrogen compressors is a thermally driven metal hydride hydrogen compressor (MHHC) which utilizes a reversible interaction of hydride-forming alloys with hydrogen gas. MHHCs have several advantages – high discharge pressures reaching 1000 bar H₂, scalability, modular design, simplicity in operation, high purity of the delivered hydrogen, and a possibility to utilise abundantly available, free to use low-grade heat. As the MHHC does not contain moving parts, this simplifies its design, increases reliability, and eliminates noise and vibration [1] making it a customer-friendly application.

HySA Systems and TF Design have developed a single-stage prototype high-pressure MHHC which is able to compress hydrogen from 100 to 700+ bar at the working temperatures 15 – 150 °C, with a productivity of 1 Nm³/h. The MHHC comprises of two 2 m-long fibre-wound high-pressure MH containers developed by the team earlier [2,3] and assembled in two modules operating in a regime of a cyclic lower-pressure H₂ absorption (when cooling) and high-pressure H₂ desorption (when heating). The containers are filled with a multicomponent C14 Laves type Ti-based AB₂ intermetallic alloy (proprietary recipe of HySA systems).

Figure 1 shows the operating high-pressure MH compressor assembly which uses water and steam for the cooling and heating. The MHHC includes medium- and high-pressure hydrogen piping, valves and fittings, pressure transmitters, water/steam piping, electric and electronic controlling components and is assembled in a stainless-steel frame, 2760(L) x 870(D) x 1800 (H).

Figure 1: General view of the high-pressure MH H₂ compressor: 1 – MH containers for high-pressure H₂ compression, 2 – steam/water distributing system, 3 – high-pressure gas manifold, 4 – pressure sensors, 5 – hydrogen coolers, 6 – PLC control block.

The presentation considers hydrogen compression performances of the utilized metal hydride alloy, metal hydride container, as well as layout and operational features of the compressor assembly. It also discusses the possibilities of its upscaling aimed at integration into the hydrogen fuelling stations.

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